

FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH PREDICTION IN GLARE HYBRID LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

A mechanistic approach for fatigue crack growth prediction in GLARE laminates is presented. Three-dimensional finite element models are used to obtain the mode I stress intensity factor, K_I , in the aluminum layers, and the fatigue crack growth rate of monolithic aluminum expressed as a Paris-type power law is used to predict the crack growth rates. To reduce computational expense, the GLARE laminates were assumed to have symmetric layups, and the finite element models were implemented via a global-local approach. The predicted crack growth rates in three different types of GLARE laminates with center-cracked tension configurations under cyclic loads obtained using the current approach are compared with experimental results. Qualitatively, the current approach predicts that the crack growth rate remains approximately constant and is independent of with crack length, which is consistent with experimental observations. The quantitative correlations with the experimental crack growth rates also show excellent agreement. It is also found that the stress intensity factors in the aluminum layers at different through-thickness locations in the GLARE laminates are not identical. The cause and implications of this discrepancy and the advantages of the current approach to predict crack growth rates in generic hybrid laminates are discussed. The current work shows that the fatigue crack growth behavior in the aluminum layers of GLARE laminates can be predicted using the fracture mechanics-based approach.

Keywords: fatigue, crack, delamination, finite element analysis, hybrid laminates

INTRODUCTION

Hybrid (or fiber metal) laminates, which consist of fiber/resin composite plies bonded with interspersed metal layers, possess superior fatigue, impact, and residual strength characteristics compared to monolithic metallic alloys [2]. The most widely researched types of hybrid laminates are ARALL (Aramid fiber composite/aluminum), TiGr (graphite fiber composite/titanium) and GLARE (glass fiber composite/aluminum). The work presented in this paper focuses on GLARE laminates and calls upon earlier work conducted on TiGr laminates. Most GLARE laminates utilize Al 2024-T3 layers interspersed with S2-glass fiber/epoxy composite plies. These laminates were developed at Delft University and have been used in several aerospace applications including the bulk cargo floor of the Boeing 777 and the bulkhead of the Learjet 125. More recently, GLARE has been selected for use in the main fuselage skin of the new, high capacity aircraft Airbus A380 [3].

With the increasing use of such hybrid laminates in aircraft primary structures, there is a need to understand the damage and failure characteristics in greater detail and to develop reliable and accurate predictive capabilities. Many investigations have been conducted to characterize and predict damage and

failure in hybrid laminates, *e.g.*, [1,4-8]. It has been shown that a key damage mode in these laminates is crack propagation in the metal layer(s) bridged by intact composite plies. Delamination between the metal layer(s) and the composite plies may occur in the wake of the crack. A diagram of this damage mode is shown in Figure 1. The intact composite plies provide a path for the applied load to be transferred across the crack faces in the metal layer(s), effectively shielding the crack tip from the full effects of the applied load. This crack bridging mechanism contributes significantly to the superior fatigue and damage tolerance characteristics of hybrid laminates compared to monolithic metals.

Models have been proposed by previous investigators to predict the fatigue crack growth behavior in hybrid laminates, *e.g.*, [1,5-8]. In some models [5,6], the effective stress intensity factor at the crack tip in the metal layer(s) and the strain energy release rate associated with the delamination in the wake of the crack are calculated analytically via a bridged crack model. The crack and delamination growth rates in the hybrid laminate are then predicted using two power law type empirical relationships; one that correlates the crack growth rate and the stress intensity factor in the monolithic metal sheet, and the other that correlates the delamination growth rate and the strain energy release rate in the hybrid laminate. Although these models have been successful in predicting crack growth behavior similar to those observed experimentally in GLARE laminates, they have yielded completely different growth trends compared to experimental observations in TiGr laminates [8]. The discrepancy was attributed mainly to the inability of the bridged crack model to capture accurately the stress and displacement profiles in the vicinity of the crack tip, which may significantly affect the behavior of the facesheet. In addition, a drawback of these models is that they require two empirical models for the crack and delamination growth rates. Such empirical relationships must be obtained via separate experiments that require a significant amount of time to perform. A model that eliminates the need for such time-consuming experiments has been proposed based on the concept of an equivalent crack length, which is hypothesized to be a material constant [7]. However, the equivalent crack length is dependent on the layup and on the crack length to a lesser degree, and requires experiments to calibrate the model.

Another approach to predict the crack growth in hybrid laminates that eliminates the need for such extensive testing has also been proposed [1,8]. In this approach, the effective stress intensity factor is obtained via three-dimensional finite element analysis and the fatigue crack growth rate of the monolithic metal expressed in terms of a Paris-type power law is used to predict the crack growth behavior. The predicted crack growth rates using this fracture mechanics-based approach have shown excellent agreement with experiments for TiGr laminates.

In the current work, the crack growth rates of the aluminum layer(s) in GLARE laminates under cyclic loads are predicted using Paris-type power laws in conjunction with crack tip stress intensity factors calculated using a 3-D finite element model. The crack growth behavior in center-crack tension (CCT) configurations is considered and comparisons of the crack growth prediction and experimental results are presented. The utility and advantages of this approach are discussed and further recommendations are made.

APPROACH

Three types of laminates with the same geometry but different ratios of aluminum to composite layers are considered in this work. The first type of laminate has four aluminum layers and three composite cross-ply (0/90 or 90/0) layers, the second type of laminate has six aluminum and five composite cross-ply layers, and the third type of laminate has eight aluminum and seven composite cross-ply layers. The layups of the three types of laminates are shown in Table 1. The laminates are 400 mm in length and 100 mm in width and contain a center hole of diameter $D = 1.5$ mm with starter notches of 0.75 mm in length. The geometry of the laminates is shown in Figure 2. The material properties of the aluminum and glass/epoxy composite materials are shown in Table 2.

The laminates were modeled using 8-noded brick elements in ABAQUS. Finite element analyses were performed for each laminate with different crack lengths in the aluminum layers. Cracks of equal length are assumed to be present in all aluminum layers in each laminate, and the composite plies are

Figure 1 Diagram of crack in metal layers bridged by composite plies and delamination in the wake of the crack [1].

assumed to be intact. The delamination in the wake of the crack in each aluminum layer is assumed to be triangular in geometry and self-similar with respect

Table 1 Layouts of GLARE laminates.

Laminate Type	Actual Layup	Assumed Layup
GLARE 3-4/3	[Al/0/90/Al/0/90/Al/90/0/Al]	[Al/0/90/Al/C ^a] _s
GLARE 3-6/5	[Al/0/90/Al/0/90/Al/0/90/Al/90/0/Al/90/0/Al]	[Al/0/90/Al/0/90/Al/C] _s
GLARE 3-8/7	[Al/0/90/Al/0/90/Al/0/90/Al/0/90/Al/90/0/Al/90/0/Al/90/0/Al]	[Al/0/90/Al/0/90/Al/0/90/Al/C] _s

^aDenotes a ply with cross-ply material properties.

to crack growth based on experimental observations. The ratio of the crack length to the length of the delamination for the GLARE 3-4/3 type laminates is 0.15, and the ratios for the GLARE 3-6/5 and GLARE 3-8/7 laminates are 0.2, where delamination length is measured from the starter notch and in x-direction [9].

The finite element analyses are used to obtain the stress and displacement fields in the vicinity of the crack tip in the aluminum layers. Using the force and displacement field results from the finite element analysis, the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) is used to calculate the strain energy release rate in the aluminum layers for the specified crack length. The mode I strain energy release rate can be calculated using the equation,

$$G_I = \frac{1}{rt_e} (u_x \cdot F_x) \quad (1)$$

where u_x is the displacement one node behind the crack tip in the x-direction, F_x is the nodal force one node ahead of the crack tip in the x-direction, r is the element size and t_e is the element thickness.

Once the strain energy release rate is obtained, the stress intensity factor can be computed using the linear elastic, plane stress relationship between the two variables for an isotropic material, *i.e.*,

$$K_I = \sqrt{E G_I} \quad (2)$$

where E is the Young's modulus of aluminum.

The fatigue crack growth rate in the aluminum layers can then be obtained using the Paris-type power law relationship for crack growth rate in monolithic Al 2024-T3. Since the power law relationship

Figure 3 Typical finite element meshes of (top) the global model, and (bottom), the two local models for GLARE 3-4/3 type laminate.

generally varies with the stress ratios, stress levels and the loading frequency, a power law from the literature is used in the current work. The power law [10] can be expressed as,

$$\frac{da}{dN} = 1.68 \times 10^{-11} (\Delta K_{eff})^{3.86} \quad (3)$$

where a is the crack length in [mm] and N is the number of cycles. The effective stress intensity factor range is used to account for plasticity induced crack closure effects [11]. The units for ΔK_{eff} is in [MPa $m^{0.5}$].

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

GLARE laminates are modeled using the finite element method with a simplifying assumption that the layups are symmetric through the thickness. This assumption is made in order to reduce the number of degrees of freedom required to model the laminates and obtain the nodal displacements and forces needed to determine the strain energy release rate. To make the layups of the laminates symmetric, the cross-ply layer in the mid-plane of each laminate is assumed to consist of two plies with the homogenized material properties of the cross-ply layer. The actual layups of the laminates considered and the assumed symmetric layups are shown in Table 1. The layers with the homogenized material properties are denoted with ‘‘C’’.

To further reduce computational expense, a global-local method is used. The global model is used to obtain the nodal displacements and forces in the entire laminate using a relatively coarse mesh, and the local model is used to consider a small region in the vicinity of the crack tip with a very fine mesh

in order to obtain more accurate values. In the global model, the smallest element size is approximately 0.61 mm in length and width, and one element is used for each aluminum or glass/epoxy composite layer.

Table 2 Material properties of GLARE laminates.

Property	S2-glass/epoxy	Property	Al 2024-T3
E_L	54.0 GPa	E	72 GPa
E_T	9.40 GPa	ν	0.33
G_{LT}	5.55 GPa	t_{Al}	0.4 mm
ν_{LT}	0.30		
ν_{TZ}	0.0575		
t	0.125 mm		

Since the entire laminate is considered in the global model, 1/8th of the laminate is modeled due to symmetries in the x and y-directions, and the assumed symmetry in the z-direction, as discussed in the previous paragraph. A typical finite element mesh of the global model is shown in Figure 3.

In the local model, the region in the vicinity of the crack tip, one element before the crack tip and one element after the crack tip in the global model, is considered. Since cracks are assumed to exist in the aluminum layers, each layer needs to be analyzed using very fine meshes through the thickness in order to obtain accurate displacements and forces at the crack tip. To keep the computational time of the local model at a minimum, multiple local models that are used to analyze each aluminum layer with very fine meshes in a laminate were used. In each local model, the aluminum layer of interest is divided into 10 elements through the thickness and the results are used to calculate the strain energy release rate in that aluminum layer only. The remaining aluminum layers are modeled using a coarser mesh of one element through the thickness. Further details of the finite element method can be found in [12].

The two local models used for the GLARE 3-3/4 type laminates are shown in Figure 3 as an example. In the first local model, the outer (facesheet) aluminum layer is modeled using 10 elements each of thickness 0.04 mm while the inner aluminum layer is modeled using one element. Since the finite element analyses yield strain energy release rates at each nodal point through the thickness in each aluminum layer, the average through-thickness value of the strain energy release rates is calculated. From this local model, the average strain energy release rate is determined for the outer aluminum layer only. In the second local model, the outer aluminum layer is modeled using one element and the inner layer using 10 elements. The average strain energy release rate is then determined for the inner aluminum layer.

Figure 4 Normalized stress intensity factors in the aluminum layers of GLARE 3-4/3 type laminates.

Figure 5 Normalized stress intensity factors in the aluminum layers of GLARE 3-6/5 type laminates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stress intensity factors (SIF) and the predicted fatigue crack growth rates in the aluminum layers for the three types of laminates considered are presented in this section. The predicted crack growth rates are compared with experimental values obtained for specimens with two center holes and starter notches under various loading conditions [9]. Two center holes were used to obtain two sets of data from a single test. The specimens with layups identical to the three types of laminates considered herein were tested under cyclic tensile load using a stress ratio (R-ratio) of 0.05 at a frequency of 10 Hz.

The SIFs for the three types of specimens are shown in Figures 4 through 6. For each type of laminate, the SIF in each aluminum layer and the average SIF of all the aluminum layers are shown. The aluminum layers are numbered starting with the outermost layer as layer 1 and increasing with the distance from the outer surface. The stress intensity factor is normalized by the applied far-field stress in the aluminum layers, σ_{Al} , multiplied by the square root of the thickness of one aluminum layer, t_{Al} . The applied far-field stress in the aluminum layer is calculated using classical laminated plate theory [13].

For all three laminates, it can be seen that the average SIFs initially decrease with increasing crack length up to approximately $0.06a/W$ and subsequently increases very gradually. Overall, the value of the average SIFs remain approximately constant with respect to crack length, implying that the crack growth rate will not increase with an increase in the crack length in the aluminum layers. Such behavior is consistent with previous experimental observations reported in the literature, *e.g.*, [4], and as presented in the following paragraphs.

The SIFs of the aluminum layers in each type of laminate is different, with the SIF of the outermost aluminum layers (Al layer 1) being greater than those of the inner aluminum layers. For example, in the GLARE 3-4/3 type laminate in Figure 5, the SIF in Al layer 1 is greater than that in Al layer 2 by approximately 20%. This implies that, in general, the crack growth rates in the outer aluminum layers are greater than those in the inner aluminum layers, and therefore, the crack length will not be identical in all of the aluminum layers in each laminate as assumed in the current work. Such behavior has also been reported in a previous experimental investigation on GLARE 3-5/4 type laminates [14]. This is caused by bridging of the inner aluminum layers by the adjacent composite layers on both sides of the aluminum that help retard crack growth. The outer aluminum layers are constrained by composite

Figure 6 Normalized stress intensity factors in the aluminum layers of GLARE 3-8/7 type laminates.

Figure 7 Normalized stress intensity factors along the thickness in an outer aluminum layer and an inner aluminum layer of GLARE 3-6/5 type laminate with a crack length of 12.12 mm.

layers on only one side while the other side, which corresponds to the outer surface of the laminate is unconstrained and free to deform out-of-plane. Typical through-thickness variations of the SIFs in the inner and outer aluminum layers in Figure 7 illustrate this mechanism. In the inner aluminum layer, the SIFs at the two sides, $z/t_{Al} = 0$ and $z/t_{Al} = 1$, are smaller than those in the interior regions of the aluminum, while in the outer aluminum layer, the SIF at one side corresponding to the outer surface, $z/t_{Al} = 0$, is greater than the other side, $z/t_{Al} = 1$.

Another effect of the constraint provided by the composite plies for the outer aluminum layers is an out-of-plane deformation of the delaminated and cracked region. This “bulging” effect is shown in Figure 8 and occurs due to the Poisson contraction of the intact composite plies of the laminate. Only the outer aluminum layers exhibit this type of deformation, and the inner aluminum layers are constrained by the composite plies to deform in-plane.

The predicted and experimental fatigue crack growth rates as a function of the applied SIF in the aluminum layers for the GLARE 3-4/3 type laminate under a maximum cyclic stress of 100 MPa is shown in Figure 9. The applied SIF in the aluminum layers are calculated using a standard solution for a monolithic center-cracked plate [15]. In general, it can be seen that the predicted crack growth rate show a similar trend compared to the experimental results although it consistently underestimate the growth rate in most cases by a factor of approximately 8. Similar results are obtained for the two other laminate cases [12].

Given that the current growth predictions consistently underestimate the experimental values, the power law in equation (3) can be calibrated to one of the experimental results to predict the growth rates in the other cases. The coefficient in equation (3) is multiplied by a factor of 8 such that the experimental results for the GLARE 3-4/3 laminate under maximum cyclic stress of 100 MPa is matched. This results in a new power law:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = 13.44 \times 10^{-11} (\Delta K_{eff})^{3.86} \quad (4)$$

The predicted and experimental fatigue crack growth rates for the GLARE 3-6/5 and GLARE 3-8/7 laminates are shown in Figures 10 and 11, respectively. As expected, it can be seen that the predicted values show excellent agreement with the experimental results. The exception is for the GLARE 3-8/7 laminate under a maximum cyclic stress of 80 MPa. In this case, the predicted growth rate significantly underestimates the experimental growth rate by a factor of approximately 12. Note, however, that the experimental growth rate in this case is comparable to the case of the same laminate under maximum

Figure 8 Deformed model of GLARE 3-6/5 type laminate with a crack length of 12.12 mm showing typical out-of-plane deformation in the outer aluminum layer.

Figure 9 Predicted and experimental fatigue crack growth rates in GLARE 3-4/3 type laminate under a maximum cyclic stress of 100 MPa using a generic power law (eq. (3)).

Figure 10 Predicted and experimental fatigue crack growth rates in GLARE 3-6/5 type laminates under maximum cyclic loads of 80 MPa, 100 MPa, and 120 MPa using calibrated power law (eq. (4)).

cyclic stress of 100 MPa. Since a lower cyclic stress implies a smaller SIF, the growth rate for the 80 MPa case should intuitively be smaller than the case when 100 MPa is applied. This indicates that the experimental result may be in error and that the gross underestimation of the predicted growth rate may be an anomaly.

It is likely that the discrepancy between the prediction made with the literature Paris law and the experimental results is due to a combination of two factors. Firstly, the GLARE laminates use relatively thin metal foils whose thickness is 0.4 mm, whereas the da/dN data was obtained from thicker specimens on the order of 2 mm. The difference in specimen thickness and the accompanying grain structure may well have an effect on crack growth. Secondly, residual stresses are likely to be introduced during manufacturing and this will alter the effective R-ratio from the value due to the applied loading. This in turn will alter the crack growth response. This latter effect was found to be important in the previous work on TiGr [8].

CONCLUSION

The current work shows that the fatigue crack growth behavior in the aluminum layers of GLARE laminates can be predicted using a linear elastic fracture mechanics approach. In this approach, the stress intensity factor at the crack tip is obtained using a three-dimensional finite element analysis and fatigue crack growth rate is predicted using a power law relationship for crack growth in monolithic aluminum sheets. The stress intensity factors obtained for various crack lengths in all three types of laminates are relatively constant, which implies that the crack growth rate remains constant with increasing crack length. Qualitatively, this trend is in good agreement with the experimental results. The predicted fatigue crack growth rates were found to slightly underestimate the experimental values when a power law relationship for the monolithic aluminum sheets from the literature was used, while excellent agreement was seen when a power law relationship calibrated on one of the experimental results was used.

Figure 11 Predicted and experimental fatigue crack growth rates in GLARE 3-8/7 type laminates under maximum cyclic loads of 80 MPa, 100 MPa, and 120 MPa using calibrated power law (eq. (4)).

The results presented herein show that crack growth rates in the aluminum layers at different locations through the thickness may not be identical. Due to the difference in the number of composite plies adjacent to the aluminum layers bridging the crack, the stress intensity factors at the crack tip in the outermost aluminum layers are greater than those in the inner aluminum layers in all three types of laminates considered. Therefore, cracks in outermost aluminum layers are expected to grow at a faster rate compared to those in the inner aluminum layers. Another difference between the outermost and inner aluminum layers is that former are free to deform out-of-plane due to Poisson contraction when the laminate is under tension while the latter are constrained to deform in-plane due to the intact composite plies. The effect and significance of this discrepancy in the boundary conditions of the aluminum layers are unclear and needs further investigation.

The main advantages of the current approach are that it is easy to use and yields reliable and accurate predictions for the crack growth. The good agreement between the predicted and experimental results from the current work for GLARE laminates along with those from previous work [1,8] for TiGr laminates gives confidence that the current approach can be used to predict crack growth in any type of hybrid laminates. Other analytical models such as the bridged crack model was shown to yield inaccurate results for the TiGr laminate. This modeling capability is of great significance for both the material/laminate selection phase of design and for the application of in-service inspection and maintenance plans.

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